

A. NATO ȘI PROBLEMELE GLOBALE ALE SECURITĂȚII

The Transatlantic relationship in flux: expectations, continuity and changes*

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Ever since the end of the WWII, the US has played the crucial role in advancing and promoting a strong partnership between US and Europe rooted in their shared commitment to free market and an open international trading system, to building strong alliances and to supporting an international order based on shared interests, values, rules and principles. The transatlantic relationship became the core construct shaping the post-war systemic configuration and defined the way in which both the Americans and Europeans look at each other and related to the others. The cooperation between the EU and NATO grounded the transatlantic security system founded on several key and interconnected pillars: NATO, European Union, close bilateral ties between the US and its allies from Western and Central Europe, strong commercial, investment and trade relations.

Trump's agenda of actions: a change but not exactly a shift / The way in which Trumps has changed the transatlantic paradigm

The transatlantic partnership benefited of a strong bipartisan support during successive

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American administrations and despite various shortcomings (see the Iraq crisis of 2003), it remained the core feature guiding the agenda of actions and interests between the US and Europe. The results of the 2016 Presidential elections brought about – as many analysts and experts were quick to announce – a paradigmatic shift that was to change the course of US-Europe relations as we knew before¹.

In fact, the general foreign policy orientation adopted by the Trump administration integrated elements of both change and continuity that overlapped along his years in office. On several important dossiers like Russia, Ukraine and NATO deterrence posture in the East, Trump administration adopted a staunch approach, even tougher than the previous administration. The sanctions regime imposed over Russia's invasion of Crimea in 2014 have not been lifted, Trump approved the sale of lethal weapons to Ukraine – a decision that Barack Obama was reluctant to take – and he has ordered missile fires at Syrian military sites, openly targeting strategic operations and allies of Russia². Moreover, he decided to expel 60 Russian diplomats in retaliation against Russia following the poisoning of former KGB agent Sergei Skripal and his daughter in the UK.

Moreover, the Trump administration has backed new NATO initiatives to deter Russian aggression, supported the accession of two new members to the alliance, and increased US troops deployment in Europe. The continued US commitment to European security was

proved through the decision to significantly strengthen the European Deterrence Initiative (EDI) whose funding reached \$5.91 billion in FY2020 from \$985 million as it was at the beginning in FY2015³. The EDI has enabled the first increase in US military forces in Europe since the end of the Cold War. As of February 2020, about 74,000 US personnel were permanently stationed in Europe.⁴

Although, President Trump showed a clear interest to continue even strengthen the existing lines of effort on specific European security dossiers, his rhetoric, behavior and way of conduct increased apprehensions in Europe and raised deep concerns regarding the US international posture and its global strategic outlook. The Trump administration was to be perceived as a “game changer” in terms of America’s new typology of world engagement, of building partnership, of complying and supporting the global institutions and of shaping the European and Euro-Atlantic security. The change in US policy orientation was obvious on two main dimensions: multilateralism and transatlantic partnership, both of them coming under Trump direct “attack” adding a sense of urgency for the European allies to manage the changes brought about by the new US’s discourse.

First, it’s about the US’s commitment towards multilateralism and Trumps’ open hostility towards the multilateral international organizations over the perceived constraints that multilateralism places on Washington’s freedom of action. This new dynamic represented - as some experts put it - a philosophical difference between Washington and European capitals. A series of actions came to deepen the apprehensions regarding the US agenda: the withdrawal from the Paris climate agreement; the decision to suspend all funding for the UN Population Fund starting in 2017; the significant budget cuts for UNAIDS and the WHO which lost about 30% and 20 % respectively of their US funding in 2018⁵; the announcement that the US would withdrawal from the WHO completely over concerns about Chinese influence amid the coronavirus pandemic; the decision to end the participation in the UN Global Compact on Migration to name some of them. In fact, Trump voiced on different occasions

his reluctance regarding the UN and asked questions about whether the world might be better off without the World Trade Organization.

The rationale behind Trump’s course of action needs to be understood as part of his broader thinking and vision regarding world politics and US interests. The 2017 US National Security Strategy (NSS) gives us more accurate insights by stating clearly that: “putting America first is the duty of our government and the foundation for US leadership in the world [...] This National Security Strategy puts America first”. The increased emphasis on sovereignty and national interests as the primary focus defining the US’s international conduct represented a shift with major strategic implications. President Trump did not miss the opportunity to remind allies around the world that the US “can no longer be taken advantage of, or enter into a one-sided deal where the United States gets nothing in return”. Citing President’s words: “As long as I hold this office, I will defend America’s interest above all else”⁶. It was such a view that raised serious concerns and apprehensions in Western European capitals.

Fears which were considered over and done came to surface. Fears about a new era of unilateral solutions, isolationism and economic protectionism – in short, the era of narrow, selfish, and self – centered vision of national sovereignty. In fact, the “Make America Great Again” story was nothing more than a different paradigm of structuring the global world order based on shadow deals following the strict national interests without considering the others. An order that was to be defined by the balance of power logic, power politics and bilateral deals instead of multilateralism and cooperation that were the founding principles of the post-Cold War security architecture. As stated by the 2017 National Security, the US strategy will focus on great power competition. In other words, a return to the old patterns of behavior that defined the conduct of the main actors on the international arena, acting on their own and outside the framework of international organizations.

Second, through its actions, Trump administration have directly questioned NATO’s

strategic value raising questions regarding the viability of the EU-US partnership. The break between EU and USA during the Trump Administration was not only a matter of philosophical difference- multilateralism versus selfish national interest- but it was a matter of existential security interest. What he did was to directly challenge the transatlantic axis, the very foundation of Euro-Atlantic security and defense. This was a fundamental change that overlooked the previous disagreements and mini-crisis within the transatlantic partnership. Ever since his election campaign, Trump referred to NATO as “absolute” and suggested Washington can no longer afford to maintain its commitment to the military alliance even mooted leaving NATO altogether. He argued that America should focus on its domestic challenges and pay less attention to problems in other parts of the world. In the president’s words: “We certainly cannot afford to do this anymore. NATO is costing us a fortune... we’re protecting Europe with NATO but we’re spending a lot of money... Why is it that Germany’s not dealing with NATO on Ukraine... Why are we always the one that’s leading, potentially, the third world war with Russia?”⁷.

The problem is not that Trump complained about the Europeans not spending enough for defense- an issue which emerged on NATO agenda even before- but the way he understands the overall question and how he put it into perspective. Of even greater concern, however, was his apparent readiness to make conditional the US commitment under Article 5 of NATO depending on whether the ally in question had “fulfilled its financial obligations to us”, specifically of it had met NATO’s 2 percent of GDP target for defense spending. The transactional approach concerning an issue of existential impact for NATO was to mark a radical departure from the foreign policy consensus in Washington towards NATO since the end of the Second World War.

So, there are two worrying aspects here. On one side, it’s about NATO and US commitment to the military alliance. On the other side, it was questioned the US willingness to remain further engaged in world affairs and assume global leadership unless there are not major American interests at play. Trump repeatedly

advocated for a light footprint in the world as to allow the US to look more inward and steer its resources towards rebuilding and developing its economy and infrastructure. The longer Trump was advancing his agenda, the more it became more obvious that the American interests were not aligned with those of the European allies.

As mentioned, Trump’s way of conduct introduced important changes, but these cannot be perceived as a complete paradigmatic shift in the transatlantic partnership. Previous US administrations voiced also the need for a more consistent increase of the defense budgets of the European allies, asked the EU to assume more responsibility in terms of security in its neighborhood, questioned the easiness of deploying troops to various remote theaters of operations and in which way these deployments meet the US national security interests, and started to refocused on the national needs at home.

But the most important factor that shaped Trump’s strategic thinking was the growing concerns over China’s geopolitical aspirations and the imperative of getting an upper hand in the coming US-China systemic competition. And here we may find the most striking pattern of continuity in terms of foreign policy that defined the US global agenda in the last decade. Trump’s focus on China was not a strategic novelty. On the contrary, the Pivot to Asia was announced long ago during the Obama’s early years in office when it became obvious that, as the State Secretary Hilary Clinton announced- that this century will be “America’s Pacific Century”⁸. The need to counter China and preserve the Western-centric systemic configuration with the US at its core came to determine the US’s strategic calculus. As a result, the US started a gradual process of moving its focus from Europe to Asia letting Europe, especially Germany, to assume a more active role in European security. The emergency posed by China was the major imperative that was to mobilize the US resources and attention. The Crimea crisis of 2014 stopped this trend but it did not reverse it. The Trump Administration adopted a more offensive approach being assumed that the US has to be prepared for a long-term competi-

tion with China that is to define the overall systemic architecture and America's ability to keep its hegemonic posture. The dynamic of the transatlantic relationship was, therefore, to be closely connected to the broader effort of stopping the Chinese geopolitical raise and to allow the US resources to be diverted towards achieving this goal.

Nevertheless, the traces left by the Trump administration on the transatlantic partnership should not be underestimated or ignored. Some of them are not necessarily new but they surfaced in a more virulent manner and they cannot simply disappear or be pushed behind under the carpet. Trump proposed a new vision, one focused on putting the American interest first even at the expense of the interests of the European allies. He rejected multilateralism, looked at the EU with hostility and treated the NATO allies from a pure transactional perspective based on the formula *you are a friend if you pay and only then you are worth to be defended*. He saw the American interests as best served through bilateral deals and agreements following the pure national interest. The others who do not comply with his proposed deals are either competitors or foes. The nationalist view focused on the American interests first and the need to counter and punish China were to dominate his course of actions. The transatlantic partnership was rather a victim of Trump's shifting agenda of priorities coupled with his nationalistic commercial-tailored thinking. The main question remained: was the Trump presidency an accident or rather did it speak about a trend that is going to further shape the US's posture, its global engagements and transatlantic partnership?

The new US administration's perspective on the transatlantic relationship and global security

As expected, the election of President Biden has risen new hopes in the European capitals and renewed expectations concerning the improvement of EU-US relations. The Interim National Security Strategic Guidance re-

leased by President Biden in March 2021 gave us the first important insights into the vision of the new administration aiming at reshaping US's global role and international postures for the next four years. This vision put forward by the Biden team covers a broad range of issue focused on the importance of diplomacy, democracy, human rights, climate change, international institutions, security partnership as well as the major challenges posed by traditional state actors- China and Russia- and the need to end the war in Afghanistan. Certainly, the commitment to democracy and the importance of formal alliance in both Europe and Asia features as the most prominent issues on the new president's agenda and this was to send a powerful message to the world and, especially important, to the European allies, that the US will embark on a largely different course than the one pursued under the former US Administration. In doing so, the US returns to the traditional approach as a promoter and defender of a liberal world order working in concert with its allies and building on the transatlantic relationship. Reading the document one can notice that the view on the major challenges and threats is largely similar to the one crafted during the Trump mandate being emphasized the great power competition, China issue or the growing nation-state threats. The difference is made by how the new administration understands to address these increasing threats and other global challenges as the American strategy calls for more engagement, more contribution to global efforts and more coordination with allies and partners.

An important dynamic regards the transatlantic relations and the renewed interest manifested by the new President and his team to re-engage America with her European allies. The new course was announced by the President himself at the Munich Security Conference in February 2021 when he voiced clear and loud that "America is back. The transatlantic alliance is back. And we are not looking backward: we are looking forward, together". Two elements are especially important: "transatlantic alliance" and "together". In this logic, he reasserted the return to the traditional approach that sees the partnership between Europe and the United States as the cornerstone

of “our security”. The powerful message sent by the new President included the three key commitments: to NATO, to article 5 of collective defense and to cooperation with the European Union.

But the new president understands that NATO needs to do more and be more relevant in tackling the complicated geography of threats which certainly will shape the US future strategic agenda. By increasing the focus on dialogue and coordination, the new president seeks to reinvigorate the political side of what NATO does, making NATO one of the key places where the most important security issues will be addressed and discussed among the alliance’ members. Why such a dynamic is important? To answer this question is important to have the big picture of the urgency of the emerging threats geography. It is obvious that the article 5 solidarity is fully understood as well as the responsibility of each member state in case of an armed attack against the territory of one member country. But the current security environment is more exposed to non-military hybrid-type challenges, an area where the things are not so clear when it comes to alliance solidarity. This is why aspects like values, interests, perceptions, behaviors need to be considered in order to increase the alliance cohesion and keep the member countries united in a common security vision. Building and keeping a stronger a networking of like-minded allies committed to democracy and democratic values is the best way to counter the advance of illiberal influences and autocratic-model and keep the countries and societies safe and more resilient in front of growing anti-democratic narratives and movements. A strong democratic model at home is the perquisite to build and advance the democratic world order abroad. Biden understands very well this dynamic especially in the light of the big concerns raised by the violent riots at the Capitol Hill in January 2021 which brought the issue of democracy at the forefront of the internal American debate. The US leadership is instrumental in forging such a course of action mixing both the hard power-art.5- and the political value-based instruments to give more substance to the transatlantic partnership.

The improvement of the relations with the EU was an important step for the Biden administration to give consistency to its new course of action. A series of announcements came to prove the willingness of the new Administration to repair de relations with the EU and the European allies and give a new boost to the transatlantic relations. One of the first decision was to cancel the order regarding the planned withdraw of the US forces from Germany. In May 2021, the US announced the decision to lift the sanctions against the main company - Nord Steam 2 AG - involved in building the North Stream 2. Antony Blinken justified the decision by stating that the sanctions “would have affected the relations between the US and Germany, European Union and other European allies and partners”. On its side, in December 2020, the European Commission and the High Representative for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy released the report “A new US-EU agenda for global change” calling for a revival of the trans-Atlantic relationship. Putting words into action, Biden and his team have been active in showing their support to the European allies. Secretary of state, A. Blinken has participated in the EU Foreign Affairs Council in Brussels in February 2021, in two NATO ministerial meetings, and in the G7 ministerial meeting in London. Engagement in smaller bilateral and regional formats with individual European countries has been also carried out. In March 2021, President Biden dialed into the EU Council meeting, the first such a move since George W. Bush in 2001. The new American agenda fully meet the European expectations as they hoped to see the US working more closely with allies and partners to reaffirm NATO and the transatlantic values, to engage more the EU in consultations as a strategic partner and avoid negative rhetoric against the EU.

Another important dynamic regards the US renewed commitment to work within a global multilateral framework, a move that was highly welcome in the European capitals and Brussels. Antony Blinken has called the multilateral system “vitaly important” and called the UN as an “anchor of the multilateral system”. In stark contrast with the “American First” policy, the new administration acknowl-

edges that there is an urgent need for a coordinated international endeavor to address the pressing global challenges that no one nation can face on its own: from climate change to nuclear proliferation and disruptive technologies, from great power competition to cyberwarfare and disinformation, mass migration and transitional terrorism. As part of the new turn towards the multilateral global setting, among the first decisions of the Biden Administration was to announce the return of US to the Paris climate agreement, to reassert the support for the World Health Organization and joined the COVAX global vaccine initiative, to restart funding the UN programs, to reconsider the US participation in the Nuclear Accord with Iran, to lift Trump-era sanctions on International Criminal Court officials, to re-engage with multilateral fora as G7 and G20. Moreover, during his first meeting with the G7 leaders, President Biden pledged for the need to coordinate multilateral action to address COVID-19, the global economic crisis, and the growing climate challenges, three important priorities and concerns on the European agenda. All these actions sent important reassuring messages to Europe and announced a new paradigm of building the US global posture.

One can easily understand that the new vision framed by the new US president is certainly a welcome change that increased the enthusiasm in Brussels while the commitment toward multilateral coordination and management brought a clear sense of relief in Europe after the turbulent years of President Trump, a staunch supporter of unilateral moves outside the multilateral framework. To give more substance to his words, President Biden has proposed a Summit of Democracy, an initiative that fully meets the EU's political goals. A summit for Democracy under the US leadership comes to prove that Washington remains committed to fight the rise of authoritarianism, to protect human rights and to strengthen trust in democracy and democratic values as the foundation of a free and stable world.

Leaving the enthusiasm aside, Biden's new vision needs to be considered in a more pragmatic and broader approach. If the present looks hopeful, the future remains marked by

growing uncertainty under the impact of rapid changes in the systemic power configuration and the return of great power competition coupled with the shifting typology of global challenges that includes pandemics, climate, cyber threats, international terrorism, hybrid warfare, or disruptive technologies. The need to manage the complicated security environment will require a differentiated geography of engagements not only with the allies and partners but also with the direct systemic competitors. While China and Russia pose major threats to US global posture, the sectorial cooperation to handle specific challenges like climate, terrorism or strategic stability (see Russia) cannot be ruled out.

China, is going to stay as the US's greatest challenge and the task to manage it will mobilize mostly of US resources and attention. This is not going to change despite the new discursive pro-globalist and multilateral approach adopted by Washington. It's true that Biden has proposed a different vision in handling the Chinese systemic challenge by pledging to work with allies and partners and forge a more coordinated agenda of action to better compete against China. The call from Washington was reciprocated by the EU which included in its strategy document on a "new agenda" with Washington the need for closer coordination on the "strategic challenge" posed by China, while NATO's draft "strategic concept" pledges on the alliance to push back on Chinese assertiveness⁹. However, the cooperative approach advanced by Biden it's more about strategy than substance. The goal remains the same: to counter China in line with American core national interests. To do that, he needs the support of the European and non-European allies. The way in which the European and global allies will respond to US's imperatives and expectations towards China may largely dictate the US's future conduct. As A. Gardner, former US ambassador to the EU, recently put it: China will be "priority No.1" for the new administration...If allies matter, they need to matter on China¹⁰. How the things will evolve remains uncertain as the interests of both-US and EU- are far from being fully aligned. A few developments are especially revealing. The EU has negotiated at the very end of 2020,

the Comprehensive Agreement on Investment (CAI) with China without any prior discussion or consultation with Washington rising questions regarding the prospects of EU-US ability and capacity to reach a full consensus on how to coordinate and forge common policies with respect to China.

The conclusion of the trilateral agreement between the US, Australia and United Kingdom on September 15, 2021 (so-called AUKUS) in a clear bid to deter China came to add new reasons of concerns among the European capitals. The implications of the new agreement are more profound since it indicates a typology of action that may define not only a new US's approach of deterring China based on small military and technological arrangements with regional allies, but also a new strategic reality, that the US is repositioning itself from the Atlantic region to the Indo-Pacific¹¹. What role the European allies are going to play in the new American's Pacific race? France's harsh reaction, besides the financial implications claimed by Paris, reveals deeper apprehensions concerning the US's willingness to accommodate in practice the interests of the other allies in the new geopolitical competition in Indo-Pacific. In other words, a conduct that may signal a rift between the discursive commitments voiced at the beginning of the mandate and the practical agenda of actions that indicates a preference for a pragmatic approach focused, first and foremost, on the US strategic interests. Of course, the American Administration cannot be blamed for trying intentionally to bypass its European allies on such an important dossier. On the contrary, and maybe this is even more worrisome, the urgency of countering and deterring China is such a pressing issue that it practically forces the US to move in a more consistent manner towards the Asian theater. For Paris, the emergence of AUKUS opens a new opportunity to claim the need for the EU strategic autonomy, a strategic vision that remains subject of vivid debates between the Eastern and Western halves of Europe. One thing is obvious: China will continue to dominate the US's agenda of priorities and its way of conduct towards within the broader global setting. The way in which the European allies would adjust their actions

and expectations to the new reality would significantly shape the overall dynamic of the transatlantic partnership.

Undoubtedly, Biden is a staunch supporter of NATO and transatlantic partnership. His belief in NATO and in the imperative of US's commitment to European defense largely shapes his strategic vision. From this perspective, the next four years will be safer and more predictable but not necessarily easier given the irritant issues which surfaced more prominently in the last years and which are unlikely to disappear soon. The US overall position calling for a more balanced burden-sharing within NATO and increased contribution of the European allies to the joint allied defense efforts will remain unchanged. The same with the US plea to direct NATO on a more global agenda and play a more prominent role on tackling a broader range of challenges. While the US will continue to provide for collective defense, is highly expected that President Biden will continue to put pressures on Europe to take on more of the security burden that includes spending more on defense, capabilities and contributions to operational commitments. Here, again, the task will not be easy to fulfill.

While the US will need to free more resources to cope with the China challenge, this will inevitably shape its involvement and expectations with NATO that may include a more cautious path as regards the foreign involvements in various theaters of conflict around the globe. The prospects of having NATO adopting a more pro-active role are also less likely in terms of NATO enlargement, increased US troops deployments in the east or strengthening deterrence measures on the Eastern flank. The commitment for the article 5 will be central to the US agenda but the new administration will be careful about assuming additional engagements than those already in place. The focus will be rather on the allied countries to take action in order to enhance their resilience, consolidate their defense potential and contribute more to collective defense.

Russia is another issue on the US-EU agenda. Undoubtedly, both parties shared a similar vision concerning Russia's aggressive

posture and the challenge she poses to continental security. The way in which the Russian challenge should be managed, however, is not so certain on the two sides on the Atlantic as the US inevitably will treat it in a more global setting, while the European allies are not fully united in their perception on what matters more: security (Eastern European allies) or economy (Western European allies). Reading foreign policy priorities assumed by President Biden, a major interest will be to prevent new areas of conflict to emerge in Europe and allow the US to focus on more urgent pressing global issues. The engagement in strategic talks with Russia to assure military predictability is part of that security approach as confirmed by the first Biden-Putin summit in Geneva in June 2021. The strategic dialogue with Russia may also provide the US an important systemic leverage in the ongoing competition with China and may help easing Russia's bullying behavior in the east. More predictability in US's foreign policy agenda may also have a beneficial effect on the US-Russia relations and soften up Russia assertiveness but this will not change the geopolitical realities in the east and the need for NATO to draw clear red lines against Russia. At this moment, it's not well certain in which way the Biden administration may consider such a scenario and how it would look like in practice. Certainly, the renewed commitment to NATO and the article 5 of collective is also intended to act as deterrence against Russia and discourage her from aggressive moves but this strategy may not prove enough to ease the concerns of the vulnerable eastern allies.

Conclusions

There is a common agreed consensus that the strengthening of EU-NATO cooperation is urgently needed as to increase the cohesion and joint action on pressing issues such as: Russia's "aggressive actions," international terrorism, cyber threats and China's "assertiveness and growing influence." How this is going to happen is still subject of further discussion and reflection. The new NATO strategic concept and NATO 2030 initiative are intended to find important answers and generate in-

novative ideas to help NATO and the transatlantic partnership to adapt and respond more efficiently to the challenges ahead but finding solutions will not be easy.

The next four years will bring about a change of paradigm in the way in which the US will understand to build and advance its global leadership posture. It's, in fact, a return to the traditional US approach but this time the challenges the world is facing are of different nature than we used to know before and this, inevitably, will increase the pressures on the new president to find the right balance between the domestic, European, and global needs. Reading the first months in office, the US's actions reveal a concerted effort to recover its legitimacy and credibility as a global actor and once more place America at the head of the global stage, leading the world by example, through diplomacy, multilateral coordination and alliances.

This is, indeed, a much welcome move as there is a real need to rebuild trust and confidence in the US and keep it in engaged in the world affairs. This is why the speech delivered in Munich revealed a significant turn in terms of language and narrative by re-engaging the US as a responsible and trustworthy contributor to global security and stability, working jointly with the allied and partner countries and providing full support to multilateralism as a credible framework of managing global issues. Especially important for rebuilding the image of the US leadership is the way in which the new president has committed himself to be part of the solution on global important dossiers from COVID-19 pandemics and climate change to democracy, human rights, trade regulations and security and development.

Apart of all the good intentions of the new administration, the challenges facing the Biden administration are the same as in the last four years and managing them though multilateral instruments alone will not be an easy mission. The domestic demands will be inevitably high of Biden agenda either we talk about democracy and migration, managing the pandemics or supporting the American industry, protecting the American market, sharpen the innovative edge, securing the technological advance and protecting the interest of its technological cor-

poration against the disruptive actions of other actors especially China.

The commitment to transatlantic relations, to NATO and European allies, is not only a public relations strategy. President Biden is indeed a pro-Atlanticist, he trusts global institutions and believes that US can win more by remaining globally engaged than by adopting a competitive, coercive posture. But the world has changed, the great power competition is here and it's going to stay while the nature of security challenges is completely different than one decade ago and this may force him to act differently from how he speaks. The new dynamic of geopolitical competition has already moved the battleground for global power in Asia-Pacific. The global shift from the Atlantic to Pacific is already shaping the US's behavior and typology of action, as proved by the QUAD format or the recently concluded AUKUS agreement. The new strategic imperatives of the Asia theater may drive the US to seek for a broader and more flexible geography of military and security arrangements needed to deter China hegemonic ambitions and consolidate the American military posture in Asia-Pacific. Such a drift should not necessarily weaken the US's transatlantic commitment but it would require innovative approaches within NATO to allow a common platform of action to generate more solidarity in terms of interest, goals and strategic priorities among allies. And the way in which the US and the EU will be able to accommodate their views on how to handle the Chinese challenge is going to significantly define not only the dynamic of the transatlantic partnership and the future of the European security equation but also the grand design of the transatlantic-centered liberal world order.

Note

¹ Erik Brattberg, David Whineray, "How Europe Views Transatlantic Relations Ahead of the 2020 U.S. Election," 20 February 2020, <https://carnegieendowment.org/2020/02/20/how-europe-views-transatlantic-relations-ahead-of-2020-u.s.-election-pub-81049>, accessed at 22 May 2021

² "Here's where Trump has been tough on Russia – and where he's backed", 16 July 2018 down, <https://www.cn>

[bc.com/2018/07/16/heres-where-trump-has-been-tough-on-russia--and-where-hes-backed-do.html](https://www.cnbc.com/2018/07/16/heres-where-trump-has-been-tough-on-russia--and-where-hes-backed-do.html)

³ *The European Deterrence Initiative: A Budgetary Overview*, Congressional Research Service, 16 June 2020, <https://fas.org/sgp/crs/natsec/IF10946.pdf>

⁴ Ibid

⁵ "Funding the United Nations: What Impact Do U.S. Contributions have on UN Agencies and Programs?" <https://www.cfr.org/article/funding-united-nations-what-impact-do-us-contributions-have-un-agencies-and-programs>. 8 June 2020

⁶ "Trump Offers a Selective View of Sovereignty in U.N. Speech", *New York Times*, 19 September 2017 <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/09/19/world/trump-speech-united-nations.html>

⁷ "Trump questions need for NATO, outlines noninterventionist foreign policy", *Washington Post* <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/post-politics/wp/2016/03/21/donald-trump-reveals-foreign-policy-team-in-meeting-with-the-washington-post/>, 21 March 2016

⁸ "America's Pacific Century", Remarks by Hilary Clinton, State Secretary, East-West Center, November 10, 2011, <https://2009-2017.state.gov/secretary/20092013clinton/rm/2011/11/176999.htm>, accessed 18 September 2021

⁹ "What Are Biden's Actual Prospects for Reviving Trans-Atlantic Relations?", 11 January 2021, <https://www.worldpoliticsreview.com/articles/29342/what-are-biden-s-actual-prospects-for-reviving-trans-atlantic-relations>

¹⁰ "What U.S.-Europe Relations Under Biden May Look Like", <https://www.wsj.com/articles/what-u-s-europe-relations-under-biden-may-look-like-11610730165>, 15 January 2021, accessed 24 May 2021

¹¹ "Don't Underestimate the AUKUS Rift With France", 22 September 2021, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2021/09/22/aukus-france-biden-europe-allies/>, accessed at 23 September 2021

ABSTRACT

There is a common agreed consensus that the strengthening of EU -NATO cooperation is urgently needed as to increase the cohesion and joint action on pressing issues such as: Russia's "aggressive actions," international terrorism, cyber threats and China's "assertiveness and growing influence." How this is going to happen is still subject of further discussion and reflection. The future new NATO strategic concept and the NATO 2030 initiative are intended to find important answers and generate innovative ideas to help NATO and the transatlantic partnership to adapt and respond more efficiently to the challenges ahead but finding solutions will not be easy.

Keywords: Transatlantic, security, cooperation, EU, NATO, USA, EU, collective defense, China, Russia, risks

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